

4B_1a Expose your local system

Enabling your institute's local system to directly expose metadata creates the strongest connection between your original data and publicly available information. This setup means that responsibility for maintaining this metadata is kept at the source, whether handled by software or people. Achieving this requires either a system already supporting this feature or deep knowledge of the source system and the availability of software engineering capacity to extend the functionality of the system.

When considering sharing your data with the public, think about using local systems like **MOLGENIS**. These systems establish a direct pathway between your original data and public information, ensuring that you're in charge of managing your data within your institute.

Explanation

To facilitate this process, ensure that the systems in your institute support extensions for displaying metadata from your existing data sources. If your system lacks this capability, you can [4B_2a Automate export from your local system](#) as an alternative.

MOLGENIS implementation of the FDP extension.

MOLGENIS partly supports the FAIR principles, including the FAIR Data Point (FDP) extension. The FDP implementation within MOLGENIS EMX2 complies with the latest v1.1 specification of the FAIR Data Point. This means that MOLGENIS allows you to establish a connection with a FAIR Data Point. For setup and configuration instructions, please refer to the [MOLGENIS documentation](#).

Other implementations of Fair Data Point

There are several FAIR Data Point implementations in existence:

- The [reference implementation](#) as described above.
- The [MOLGENIS](#) software supports the FAIR Data Point protocol.
- [Castor](#) currently supports a previous version.
- The [Netherlands eScience Center](#) have their own [implementation](#).
- The [SURF Data Repository](#) implements the protocol.
- [RD-Nexus](#) implements the protocol.

- [LOVD](#) implements the protocol.
- [X-omics initiative](#) develop a FAIR Data Infrastructure, [FAIR Data Cube](#), which contains a [enhanced FAIR Data Point](#) as a main component in terms of its search and ranking capability.

Pros / Cons

Pro

- Responsibility of maintenance lies closest to the owner(s) of the source material

Con

- Requires extension of existing tooling

Next steps

If you have an FDP and compliant metadata ([4B Exposing metadata](#)) you can now enter the metadata into your FDP [4B_2 Metadata entry into an FDP](#) .